

Title: Electrochemical results for different separators(diaphragm and membranes)

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Description: This report presents results from the [PEACE project](#) focusing on the evaluation of hydrogen crossover behavior in different separators (diaphragms and membranes) for alkaline water electrolysis (AWE). The study investigates gas purity under unpressurized conditions.

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Electrochemical results for different separators (diaphragm and membranes)

In the light of PEACE project, the gas purity results for different separators (diaphragm and membranes) were evaluated.

The gas purity was evaluated using different separators under alkaline conditions. The tests

Figure 1 Plot showing the gas purity of the tested separators in the full set up at varying load range in 30wt% KOH at (a)70 °C and (b) 80 °C.

were done for the different separators at 30 wt.% KOH at two different operational temperatures 70 and 80 °C (Figure 1a and 1b). Hydrogen permeation is an important phenomenon for alkaline water electrolyser (AWE), due to several reasons particularly related to safety issues. Figure 1 shows the H₂ in O₂ content in a wide current density range up to 1.6 A cm⁻² for different separators (diaphragm and membranes). The gas impurity is mainly influenced by the proportion of hydrogen within the oxygen, given that hydrogen crossover occurs more readily than oxygen crossover. As the current density decreases the gas purity become worse. However, for all the tested separators in the above condition, the H₂ in O₂ contents at low current densities still remain below the safety limit of 2 vol.%. All of the tested separators almost show the same range of gas purity. The target here is to have slightly higher operational temperature and pressure, therefore since Zirfon 500 having a slightly better gas purity at 80°C, Zirfon will be chosen for the next pressurized condition testing. In overall, the

above results showed promising gas quality for all the tested membranes and diaphragms. Further works in the future need to be conducted in the pressurized conditions.